

***3D'omics data and metadata
standards***

Deliverable 5.3 (UCPH)

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General project information

Title	Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production
Acronym	3D'omics
Grant Agreement No.	101000309
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Instrument	RIA (Research and Innovation Action)
Project start date	01/09/2021
Duration of the project	52 months

Project partners

#	Partner	Abbrev	Type	Country
1	University of Copenhagen	UCPH	University	Denmark
2	Center for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Research Center	Spain
3	Veterinary University of Vienna	UVM	University	Austria
4	Max Delbrück Center	MDC	Research Center	Germany
5	KU Leuven	KUL	University	Belgium
6	ETH Zurich	ETH	University	Switzerland
7	Ben Gurion University	BGU	University	Israel
8	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NMBU	University	Norway
9	Afekta Technologies Limited	ATL	Industry, SME	Finland
10	Aviagen, Inc.	AVI	Industry	United Kingdom
11	Novogene Netherlands B.V.	NGE	Industry	The Netherlands
12	Biomin, GmbH	BIO	Industry	Austria
13	Norsvin SA	NOR	Industry	Norway
14	Center for Genomic Analysis	CNAG	Research Center	Spain

Introduction

The generation of micro-scale molecular data adds an additional layer of complexity to the inherently intricate nature of molecular datasets. Unlike macro-scale data, each microsample collected from intestinal tissues represents only a small fraction of a larger sample, necessitating the collection of essential metadata for effective downstream analysis. Within the 3D'omics project, we have developed standardised procedures for the generation, processing, and archiving of this data. This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the established and implemented protocols.

Data types

In 3D'omics, multiple types of quantitative biological data have been generated, each characterised by distinct data structures, resolutions, and handling requirements. These data types are primarily distinguished along two dimensions:

- **Scale** – Macro, meso, and micro
- **Modality** – Sequencing, mass spectrometry, and imaging

Macro vs meso vs. micro scale data

The data generated in 3D'omics can be categorised into three groups based on their origin, physical scale, and the methods used for their generation: macro-scale, meso-scale, and micro-scale data.

Macro-scale

Macro-scale data are derived from intestinal or faecal samples collected from individual animals. Intestinal samples represent a single time point per animal, typically collected at the time of slaughter. In contrast, faecal samples are collected longitudinally, with multiple time points per individual. These samples consist of large volumes of bulk biological material and lack spatial structure.

Meso-scale

Meso-scale data originate from thin intestinal cross-sections (typically 10 μm thick), referred to as microsections, obtained from various regions of the intestine. Each animal can contribute multiple microsections. These serve as the basis for imaging and metabolomics data generation and also form the foundation for subsequent micro-scale sampling.

Micro-scale

Micro-scale data represent small, spatially resolved portions of microsections, typically ranging from 500 to 5000 μm^2 , collected via laser microdissection. The precise x-y

coordinates and sampled area are recorded as metadata, enabling spatially informed downstream analyses.

Sequencing vs. mass-spectrometry vs. imaging data

The data generated in 3D'omics can also be classified based on the modality of data generation: sequencing, mass spectrometry, and imaging. Each modality involves distinct workflows, produces data in different formats, and requires tailored downstream analysis approaches.

Sequencing data

Sequencing data, whether derived from macro- or micro-scale samples and regardless of nucleic acid type (e.g., DNA or RNA), is generated by converting DNA molecules into sequencing libraries. These libraries are then processed using high-throughput sequencing technologies. In 3D'omics, both short-read sequencing (Illumina) and long-read sequencing (PacBio HiFi) have been employed. The resulting raw data are provided in FASTQ format, containing both nucleotide sequences and associated quality scores. These data are used for genome reconstruction, as well as quantification of genome and gene abundances. All raw sequencing files are archived in public repositories such as the **European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)**.

Mass-spectrometry data

Mass spectrometry data are generated primarily from macro- and meso-scale samples for the analysis of metabolites. These datasets are characterised by complex spectral outputs requiring sophisticated preprocessing and normalisation. In 3D'omics, standardised workflows have been implemented to ensure consistency across samples and batches. The raw and processed metabolomics data are archived and made publicly available through the **MetaboLights** repository.

Imaging data

Imaging data are generated from meso-scale intestinal microsections using a variety of high-resolution microscopy techniques, including brightfield and fluorescence imaging. These images are essential for spatially contextualising molecular data and guiding microdissection. Imaging datasets are stored in standard high-resolution formats and archived through the **BioImage Archive**, ensuring accessibility and interoperability for further spatial analysis and visualisation.

Hierarchical data structure

The different types of 3D'omics raw data and associated metadata are stored in various databases hosted by the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI). The connection between raw datasets is done through Biosamples that are wrapped within Bioprojects. In the following section, the hierarchical structure of the data is explained.

Bioprojects

A BioProject is a structured and centralised record in public biological databases that organises and links together data related to a specific biological research project. It serves as an umbrella to group all datasets generated as part of a single research initiative or study. Each BioProject is assigned a unique accession number that researchers can cite to refer to the entire project and access all associated datasets. A BioProject record includes title and description of the study, submitter and institution information and links to associated datasets

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>

In 3D'omics, we have an Umbrella Bioproject for the entire project (**PRJEB86267**) and dedicated Bioprojects for each experiment.

Bioproject	Study	Link
PRJEB100724	Proof-of-concept fibre swine trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB100724
PRJEB86255	Adenovirus challenge poultry trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86255
PRJEB86258	Salmonella challenge chicken trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86258
PRJEB86259	Histomonas challenge turkey trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86259
PRJEB86260	Histomonas challenge chicken trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86260
PRJEB86261	Mannan fibre swine trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86261
PRJEB86262	Protein digestibility swine trial	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB86262

Biosamples

A BioSample is a standardised metadata record describing the biological source material from which data—such as sequencing, metabolomics, or imaging—are derived. Each BioSample represents a single, unique biological specimen and includes essential contextual information such as organism, tissue type, sampling method, geographic origin, and experimental conditions. BioSample records are linked to the corresponding datasets (e.g., sequencing runs in the SRA or ENA), enabling traceability and reproducibility. Each BioSample is assigned a unique accession number and can be reused across multiple datasets or publications if derived from the same specimen.

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

Importantly, BioSample records can be organised into nested hierarchies, reflecting the biological or experimental structure of a study. This hierarchical organisation allows researchers to model relationships between samples—for example, between a whole organism and its derived tissues or sub-samples.

In 3D'omics, we leverage this capability to represent the multi-scale nature of our sampling strategy:

- **Animal-level BioSamples:** represent individual animals from which all downstream samples originate.
- **Macrosample-level BioSamples:** represent macro-scale samples, such as faeces, intestinal contents or tissue samples from which sequencing and mass-spectrometry data are generated.
- **Microsection-level BioSamples:** represent thin intestinal cross-sections derived from specific regions of the gastrointestinal tract of those animals.
- **Microsample-level BioSamples:** represent small, spatially resolved tissue regions obtained from microsections through laser microdissection.

This hierarchical structure enables precise traceability and integration across macro-, meso-, and micro-scale data, supporting spatially informed multi-omic analyses and robust data reuse.

Raw datasets

At the final level of the data structure are the raw datasets, which contain the actual output of sequencing, mass spectrometry, or imaging workflows. These datasets are organised into two types of metadata records: Experiments and Runs.

An Experiment record describes the technical and methodological details of how data were generated from a BioSample. This includes information such as the library preparation protocol, sequencing platform (e.g., Illumina, PacBio), target molecule (e.g., DNA, RNA), and strategy (e.g., whole-genome sequencing, metagenomics, transcriptomics).

A Run record points to the actual data files generated from that experiment—for example, FASTQ files in the case of sequencing. Each run represents a single instance of data acquisition, and multiple runs can be associated with one experiment, especially in cases involving technical replicates or multi-lane sequencing.

Both Experiment and Run records are directly linked to their corresponding BioSample, ensuring full traceability from the raw data back to the original biological material.

Metadata templates

To ensure consistency, completeness, and interoperability of the data generated in 3D'omics, we use standardised metadata templates across all levels of data submission. These templates define both mandatory and optional fields for BioProject, BioSample, and Run records, enabling structured metadata capture tailored to each data type and scale. Each metadata level includes:

- **Mandatory fields [M]:** required by public repositories (e.g., ENA, NCBI) to register and publish the record. These fields ensure basic identification, traceability, and compatibility across systems.
- **Optional project-specific fields [O]:** In 3D'omics, we have extended the metadata schema by defining optional fields relevant to our multi-scale, multi-modal design. These fields capture critical contextual details that improve interpretability and enable cross-modal integration.

Study level BioProject

The study-level BioProject defines each independent trial conducted within 3D'omics, wrapping all different types of datasets generated within and stored in different databases, including ENA, Bioarchive Images and Metabolights.

Field	Description	Format	Type
Project Title	A concise, descriptive title for the overall study or research project.	Short text	M
Project Description	A brief overview summarising the goals, scope, and design of the study.	Long text	M
Submitter Name	The name of the individual or organisation submitting the data.	Short text	M
Submitter Affiliation	Institution or research organization responsible for the project.	Short text	M
Public Release Date	The date when all the embedded data will become publicly available.	Date	M

Animal-level BioSample

Individual-level BioSamples define each biological experimental unit. In the case of animal trials, these are animal individuals, while in the case of in vitro studies refer to bioreactors or similar experimental units. This level applies to all downstream analyses, both at the macro- and the micro-scale. The metadata associated with these entries includes key information about group assignment, treatment and performance indicators, which are essential to associate microbiome features with animal production.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
Name	Unique individual animal identifier	G105	Short text	M
taxId	NCBI taxid of the host organism	9031	Code	M
Project	Name of the main project: 3D-omics	3D-omics	Short text	M
Bioproject	Umbrella bioproject code of 3D-omics	PRJEB86267	Code	M
Organism	Scientific name of the host organism	Gallus gallus	Short text	M
Trial	Bioproject code of the trial	PRJEB86258	Code	M
Treatment	A brief overview summarising the goals, scope, and design of the study.	TG1	Short text	M
Sex	Sex of the host organism	female	Short text	M

Checklist	Code of the employed checklist	BSDC00001	Code	M
Child samples	Biosample identifiers of related entries	SAMEA11778 9493	Code	O

Macrosample-level BioSample

Macrosample-level BioSamples are only defined for macro-scale datasets, including sequencing- and mass spectrometry-based data. Each entry refers to a physical sample from which the quantitative data were generated. The metadata associated with these entries includes details about the collection and preservation of the sample.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
Name	Unique microsection identifier	G002aM	Code	M
Organism	Scientific name of the host organism	Gallus gallus	Short text	M
taxId	NCBI taxId of the host organism	9031	Code	M
Origin	Intestinal section or material from which the sample derives	Caecum	Code	O
Type	Type of biological material	Tissue	Code	O
Container	Type of container in which the sample was collected	2 ml tube	Short text	O
Preservative	Type of preservative in which the sample was maintained	Shield buffer	Short text	O
Storage	Storage conditions of the sample	-70 °C	Short text	O
Parent sample	Biosample identifier of the animal specimen from which this sample derived.	SAMEA1185 45877	Code	M

Microsection-level BioSample

Microsection-level BioSamples are only defined for meso- and micro-scale datasets, including sequencing-, imaging- and metabolomics-based data. Each microsection refers to a thin cross-cut sample collected through a cryo-slicing an intestinal segment. The metadata associated with these entries includes the intestinal section as well as technical details of sample preparation.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
Name	Unique microsection identifier	G121eI102A	Code	M
Organism	Scientific name of the host organism	Gallus gallus	Short text	M
taxId	NCBI taxId of the host organism	9031	Code	M
Slide	Unique slide identifier	G121eI102	Code	O
Position	Position of the cryosection in the slide (A, B, C)	A	Code	O
Date	Date of the cryosection preparation	1/29/2024	Date	O
Child samples	Biosample identifiers of related entries	SAMEA1177 89493	Code	O

Microsample-level BioSample

Microsample-level BioSamples refer to each individual sample collected through laser microdissection. The main distinctive feature of these entries is the spatial coordinates that allow locating the exact positioning of each sample within a given microsection. In that regard, two types of coordinates are: i) the physical coordinates, indicating the absolute positions of each microsample at the microscope stage in micrometers, and ii) the virtual coordinates, indicating the positioning of each microsample in the overview image in pixels. The latter are calculated through the custom-made software **lmdmap**, which is introduced in the following section.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
alias	Unique identifier of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
title	Title of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
sample_alias	Alias of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
taxon_id	NCBI taxId for gut metagenome	749906	Code	M
sample_description	Spatially referenced intestinal microsample	Spatially referenced intestinal microsample	Short text	M
sample collection method	Method through which the sample was collected: laser microdissection	Laser microdissection	Short text	M
project name	Name of the main project: 3D-omics	3D-omics	Short text	M
collection date	Date in which the sample was collected	12/03/2022	Date	M
geographic location (latitude)	Latitude in which the sample was collected	48.255	Number	M
geographic location (longitude)	Longitude in which the sample was collected	16.428	Number	M
geographic location (region and locality)	Locality in which the sample was collected	Vienna	Short text	M
broad-scale environmental context	Ontology code of the environment in which the sample was collected	ENVO:00000078	Code	M
local environmental context	Type of environment in which the sample was collected	Experimental farm	Short text	M
environmental medium	Animal	Animal	Short text	M
geographic location (country and/or sea)	Country in which the sample was collected	Austria	Short text	M
host common name	Common name of the host organism	Chicken	Short text	M

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
alias	Unique identifier of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
title	Title of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
sample_alias	Alias of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
host subject id	Unique individual animal identifier	G105	Short text	M
host taxid	NCBI taxid of the host organism	9031	Code	M
host body site	Body site from which the sample was collected	caecum	Short text	M
host life stage	Developmental stage of the host organisms	juvenile	Short text	M
host sex	Sex of the host organism	female	Short text	M
cryosection	Unique microsection identifier	G121eI102A	Code	O
Xcoord	X-axis absolute coordinate of the microsample, to be employed for spatial analyses	23423	Number	O
Ycoord	Y-axis absolute coordinate of the microsample, to be employed for spatial analyses	14252	Number	O
Xpixel	X-axis pixel coordinate of the microsample, to be employed for visualisations	564	Number	O
Ypixel	Y-axis pixel coordinate of the microsample, to be employed for visualisations	324	Number	O
size	Area of the microsample in micrometers	5312	Number	O
buffer	Lysis buffer employed	B11	Short text	O
sampletype	Type of collected sample: positive, membrane control, lysis control or library control.	Positive	Short text	O

Sequencing dataset metadata

The sequencing dataset linked to the macrosample and microsample-level Biosamples contains technical information of the sequencing run.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
alias	Unique identifier of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
title	Title of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
sample_alias	Alias of the sequencing dataset	M300650	Short text	M
design_description	Sequencing dataset type description	metagenome	Short text	M
library_name	Unique identifier of the library	G121eI102Z 001_L1	Short text	M
library_strategy	Strategy employed for library preparation	WGS	Code	M
library_source	Type of sequencing library prepared	METAGENOMIC	Code	M
library_selection	Whether a selection procedure was used to build the sequencing library	RANDOM	Code	M
library_layout	Whether single-end or paired-end sequencing was conducted	PAIRED	Code	M

insert_size	Average number of nucleotides aimed for when library preparation	400	Number	M
library_construction_protocol	Protocol employed for sequencing library preparation	ULV2_Full	Short text	M
platform	Platform used for sequencing	Illumina	Short text	M
instrument_model	Instrument model used for sequencing	Illumina NovaSeq X	Short text	M

Metabolomics dataset metadata

The metadata corresponding to the metabolomics data stored in Metabolights is split into two tables.

Sample metadata

Containing information about the origin of the sample.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
Protocol REF	Identifier for sample collection, described in project "Protocols"	Sample collection	Short text	M
Sample Name	Sample name	C005K	Code	M
Source Name	Sample name	C005K	Code	M
Organism	Organism	Sus scrofa domesticus	Short text	M
Organism part	Organism part	caecum	Short text	M
Treatment group	Treatment group for the sample	T1	Code	O
Time point	Sample collection time point	21	Code	O
BioSamples accession	BioSamples accession code	SAMEA120497292	Code	O

Assay metadata

Containing information about the mass-spectrometry assay employed to generate the data.

Field	Description	Example	Format	Type
Sample Name	Sample Name	C005K Extraction_blank_1	Code	M
Protocol REF	Identifier for Extraction, Chromatography, Mass spectrometry, Data transformation and Metabolite identification, described in the project "Protocols"	Chromatography	Short text	M
Extract name	Sample Name	C005K	Code	M
Chromatography instrument	Manufacturer and model for chromatography instrument	Agilent 1290 Infinity II UHPLC	Short text	M
Autosampler model	Manufacturer and model for autosampler	Agilent 1290 Infinity II Multisampler	Short text	M

Column model	Manufacturer and model for column	Acquity UPLC® BEH Amide column (2.1 Å - 100 mm, 1.7 µm, Waters Corporation)	Short text	M
Scan polarity	Scan polarity value	positive	Short text	M
Scan m/z range	Scan m/z range	50 - 1600		M
Instrument	Manufacturer and model for mass spectrometry instrument	Agilent 6546 LC/Q-TOF	Short text	M
Ion source	Type of the ion source	Electrospray ionization	Short text	M
Raw Spectral Data File	Location and filename for the raw spectral data file	FILES/RAW/230206 ST_3DO_dilution_C_S_Proof_Hilic_pos_006.d.zip	Short text	M
Metabolite Assingment File	File name for the identified metabolites	m_MTBLS13210_L C-MS_positive_hilic_metabolite_profilin_g_v2_maf.tsv	Short text	M

Imdmap software

The Leica LMD7 laser microdissection microscope and its associated software Leica Laser Microdissection v8.5 (8.5.0.09136), do not provide a streamlined way to provide detailed overviews of microsample collections within their spatial context. Therefore, we developed our own software to generate such overviews for seamless browsing of microsamples over microsections.

< Input slide overview image

Output cropped image

Output cropped and marked image

Output pixel coordinate table

ID	Xcoord	Ycoord	size	shape	cryosection_text	SampleType	Xcoord_pixel	Ycoord_pixel	Xcoord_pixel_crop	Ycoord_pixel_crop	
0	rec0989YchISGjstLw	9269.44592	15557.49332	5140	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	702.0872864864865	881.0638086577777	666.0	560.0
1	rec0W9KzLyAX9P9aX	8014.85048	16401.9456	4976	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	532.5473621621621	989.5290126222221	497.0	669.0
2	rec1o6yKzOv7Pp5w	8627.54136	14468.28696	4976	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	615.3434270270269	741.1613028622222	579.0	420.0
3	rec7y99OfcHUUJfJ	8653.96326	15097.30604	4976	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	618.9139540540541	821.9553091377777	583.0	501.0
4	rec9tvenUMqTzJbVX	8638.9824	15649.53886	4976	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	616.8895135135135	892.8865469066668	581.0	572.0
5	recB18MOQ/mWB87kp	9040.98362	15934.54342	5140	Elipse	G007b1105A	Positive	671.2140027027028	929.49379928	635.0	608.0

Usage

The minimum arguments needed to use Imdmap are the cryosection name (-n), which is used to fetch the relevant information from the 3D'omics Airtable database as well as to name the default output files, and the slide overview image (-i) from which the cropped image is generated.

By default, Imdmap creates two documents in the working directory: a CSV file containing the pixel coordinates and a JPG file of the cropped image.

The following optional arguments can also be used for defining outputs:

- -t enables defining the path and name of the CSV table.
- -o enables defining the path and name of the regular cropped image.
- -m enables defining the path and name of the cropped image with the positions of microsamples marked.

The following optional arguments can be used to manually correct the offset of the cutting points and the stretch of the image:

- -x pixel offset in the x-axis.
- -y pixel offset in the y-axis.
- -w percentage image stretch in the x axis.
- -l percentage image stretch in the y axis.
- -s size of the cropping square in pixels (default: 1000).
- -c display microsample ID codes on image.
- -d comma-separated list of undesired microsamples to be manually discarded.

Availability

Repository: <https://github.com/3d-omics/lmdmap>

License: Open-source (MIT)

Documentation: Full usage instructions and schema templates are provided in the repository README.

arch3d software

To support the organisation, standardisation, and submission of complex multi-scale metadata in the 3D'omics project, we have developed a dedicated software tool: **arch3d**, an open-source Python-based command-line tool designed to streamline the creation and validation of hierarchical metadata records for submission to public repositories such as ENA. It is tailored specifically to accommodate the structured relationships among BioProjects, BioSamples, and Runs, including the nested hierarchy that reflects our macro-, meso-, and micro-scale sampling strategy.

Key Features

- **Metadata Parsing & Validation**
 - Accepts metadata templates (e.g., Excel or TSV files) containing structured metadata.
 - Validates required and optional fields against predefined schema rules.
 - Ensures correct hierarchical linkage between BioSamples (e.g., animal → microsection → microsample).
- **Accession Management**
 - Integrates with ENA systems to prepare metadata for upload and track accession numbers.
 - Facilitates reuse of existing BioSamples or linkage to umbrella BioProjects.
- **Reproducibility & Automation**
 - Enables reproducible data registration and submission across multiple experiments and contributors.
 - Can be integrated into larger data processing pipelines or executed manually by users.

Usage

Arch3d has two main operation modes. The commands `arch3d macro` and `arch3d micro` upload macro-scale and micro-scale data and metadata to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), respectively, while the command `arch3d biosample` uploads sample metadata to the database BioSamples. Both databases are connected, and the data and samples at different levels are connected through BioSamples accessions.

The most straightforward usage is to:

1. Create the Bioproject accession (not included here)
2. Upload nucleic acid data > and retrieve their sample accessions
3. Upload specimen metadata > and link nucleic acid sample accessions

Add username and, most importantly, password wrapped with single quotes (e.g. 'Webin-XXXXX'), to ensure the shell does not interpret special characters before passing them to Arch3d

Availability

Repository: <https://github.com/3d-omics/arch3d>

License: Open-source (MIT)

Documentation: Full usage instructions and schema templates are provided in the repository README.

